

SUBSTANCE ABUSE EDUCATIONAL MANUAL

Target Population: Inter-State Commercial Drivers (ISCDs) in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

This manual has three modules, each module comprises learning objectives, note for educator, training aids used, an activity session, and a recap/Question-and-answer session. Activities 1, 2, and 3 preceded the main content of modules 1, 2, and 3 respectively, while Activity 4 was included as 'take home/lessons learnt' at the end of module 3.

Module 1 (Introduction to Drug use) 40minutes

Learning objectives

At the end of this module, participants should be able to:

1. understand the meaning of drug abuse, types of substance of abuse and magnitude of drug abuse problems
2. understand why people use drugs and other important risk factors

Note for trainer/ educator and translator

1. Technical terms should be broken down to barest minimally understandable units
2. Translators are not allowed to change the overall structure of educator's statement

Training aids

PowerPoints, handbills and posters

Methodology

Activity, presentation/discussion, recap with question and answer.

Activity 1: what is a drug of abuse? (5minutes)

The educator/trainer should ask the general participants 'what is drug abuse?' and allow feedbacks from two to three participants. The activity phase should not last for more than five minutes.

1.0 Introduction to drug use (definitions, types and magnitude of problem)

30minutes

1.1 Definitions

1.11 definition 1. Educator should explain drug of abuse as any chemical or substance that when taken into the body, can alter brain function: in terms of the way we think, we perceive things, we react emotionally to situations, and the way we behave.

1.12 definition 2. Educator should also state that Drug abuse occurs when a drug is used in pattern that is damaging the physical, mental, and or social wellbeing.

Examples of physical damages: damages to the lungs, liver, kidney, brain etc.

Examples of damages to mental health: addiction, depression and loss of touch from reality

Examples of social damages: financial losses, interpersonal relationship losses.

1.13 definition 3. Educator should add that drug abuse also occurs when drugs are used in quantity or ways not prescribed or when used for purposes not prescribed for.

1.2 Types of drugs of abuse

Educator should allow the participants to mention all the available drugs of abuse before listing the following commonly abused drugs

1. Tobacco (cigar, taaba e.t.c)
2. Alcohol (commercial e.g beer, wine, branded spirit)
3. Alcohol (non-commercial e.g emu, ogogoro e.t.c)

4. Cannabis/Indian hemp/marijuana (weed, Igbo, smoke, skunk, Arizona, Colorado, Loud, skushy etc.)
5. Mild stimulants (e.g. kolanut, orogbo, coffee).
6. Other major stimulants (e.g. Cocaine, Amphetamine, Propyl, Dexamphetamine, Ephedrine, Kwaya, Mkpururimi).
7. Sedatives (Sleeping tablets e.g., Valium, Librium, Mogadon) without prescription by doctors.
8. Opioids (Fentanyl, Heroin, Pentazocine, Tramadol, Cough syrup with codeine, Codeine tablets)
9. Sniffing agents (e.g. petrol, glue, solvents etc).
10. Anabolic steroids (Winstrol, Dianabol) without doctor's prescription.
11. Others

1.4 Magnitude of the problems of Substance abuse

Educator should state the following:

- According to the international experts, over 250 million people have used at least one drug in previous year.
- The use of substances while driving has put commercial drivers and non-commercial vehicle users at risk of injury and death from road traffic accidents.
- In fact, approximately 50% of accidents and related consequences occurring on Nigerian roads have been linked to alcohol use.
- The federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) has also reported that the very high rate of road traffic accidents is caused by driving under the influence of Alcohol.

1.5 Reasons for taking drugs

- Educator should explain familial predisposition in the following way:

There is an increased risk of using substance if a family member(s) also uses substances.

Many scientific studies have consolidated this finding.

- Educator should list the other risk factors for drug use as follows:
 1. Gender (greater risk in males than females)
 2. Role of environment (growing up in an environment with unrestricted access to drugs of abuse)
 3. Curiosity and experimentation
 4. Peer pressure
 5. Medical purpose; to ameliorate symptoms of illnesses (medical and mental illness)
 6. Social purposes (anxiety purposes including social phobias, low self-esteem)
 7. Coping with stress
 8. Fun and pleasure
 9. Religious purposes

Recap and Q&A (5minutes)

Educator should recap in two minutes by highlighting definition of drug abuse, reasons why people abuse drugs and magnitude of the problems. Then, allow for questions.

Module 2 Problems of Drug use (40 minutes)

Practical session to explain the various psychosocial and medical effects of drug use.

This would be done using an Audio Case vignette or Drug abuse jingle by FRSC, with various role plays and practical demonstrations.

Learning objective

At the end of this module, participants must be able to:

To learn some of the debilitating effects of drug use through media awareness

Note for trainer/educator and translator

Following the audio session, the trainer should highlight the different effects of drug use on the physical, mental and social health, stressing the effects of driving under the influence.

Training aids

Multimedia display e.g. PowerPoint, handbills and video clips.

Methodology

Video presentation, PowerPoint presentation

Activity 2: what are the effects of drug use on user? (5minutes)

2.0 Problem of Drug use (Practical session) (30minutes)

Fig 1: an illustration of different parts of the body drug use may damage

Recap and Q&A (5minutes)

Educator should recap in two minutes by highlighting the medical and psychosocial effects of drug abuse. Then, allow for questions.

Module 3 Drug Addiction as a medical/brain disorder (40mins)

Learning objectives

At the end of this module, participants should be able to:

1. understand that addiction is a brain disorder
2. identify addiction problems in self, co-drivers, family members, and members of the society
3. learn about help seeking (prevention, early identification, and ways to seek adequate and appropriate treatment)

Training aids

PowerPoint, handbills and posters

Methodology

Power point presentation

Activity 3: Is Drug abuse/addiction a medical, social or spiritual problem? (5minutes)

The educator/trainer should ask the general participants 'Is Drug abuse a medical, social or spiritual problem?' and allow feedbacks from five participants. The activity phase should not last for more than five minutes.

3.1 Drug Abuse as a medical/brain disorder (30minutes)

Educator should begin this module by stating that, medical science has proven that addiction to drug use is a chronic brain disease rather than problem/sign of moral failings.

3.2 Why addiction is a brain disorder?

In addition, educator should then go further stating the following evidences why addiction is a brain disorder.

- Genetics: some people are more prone because of their genetic makeup. The link is as high as 50-60% (Heritability)
- Abnormalities in amount and functions of chemicals in the brain system
- Structural abnormalities found on various advance brain scan
- Tolerance and withdrawal symptoms

Figure 2: areas of the brain involved in addiction

3.3 Identifying drug use problems in Individual or co-driver (signs and symptoms)

Educator should give the following examples as possible signs and symptoms of drug use. While they may only be used to raise suspicion for drug use, they are not specific to drug use alone.

- Undue irritability resulting in frequent fights with co-drivers, family and loved ones.
- Withdrawal to self, avoidance of social functioning, meetings etc.
- Impairment in functioning manifesting as deteriorating physical care/ hygiene, deteriorating interpersonal relationship and reduced level of performance as driver
- Sleep problems (reduced/ increased)
- Appetite problems
- While driving, one may notice reduced concentration, frequent yawning, hands and body shaking, sweatiness, increased heart beats, restless and generally increased level of discomfort.

3.4 Seeking help (prevention, early Identification, overview on methods of treatment, and how/where to get help?)

3.41 Prevention

The following are preventive strategies to be discussed by the educator:

- Involves education and health awareness, this should involve training of drivers on drug use and its harmful effects
- Government policy to regulate production, distribution and sales of psychoactive substances.
- The various transport unions can also regulate availability and accessibility within their various motor parks. This helps to reduce harmful and hazardous use of substances.

- Enforcing National blood alcohol concentration limit for commercial drivers, before they embark on any journey.
- Routine drug toxicology for commercial drivers.

3.42 Early identification

- This involves early identification of aforementioned signs and features that may point to drug use.
- The goal of early identification is to facilitate early treatment, so as to reduce complications and death associated with drug use.

3.43 Overview of treatment

- A person with drug abuse problems is usually treated by specialist at any registered medical drug abuse centres in the country, e.g. the Drug And Alcohol Treatment, Educational And Rehabilitation- DATER centre at University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital.

3.44 Treatment involves:

Managing complications and immediate problems like (withdrawal symptoms, attendant medical problems e.g. body wounds for injectors, psychiatric problems e.g. depression, psychosis)

Educator should explain technical terms as described below:

Depression: undue sadness, loss of interest in pleasurable activities, feeling of worthlessness and hopelessness, suicidal intents and thoughts etc.

Psychosis: when there is loss of touch with reality resulting in hearing voices not heard by others or/ seeing things not seen by others.

3.45 Helping the drug user remain free of drug use.

This is done through drug rehabilitation.

What Are Your Roles as A Driver in The Prevention and Treatment of Drug Abuse?

1. Drug compliance and adherence, for some one that has seen a specialist and has been placed on medications
2. Counselling and helping other people with drug use problems
3. Appropriate referral (DATER centre and other drug treatment centres across the country including their clinic days)

Activity 4: take home, lessons learnt

Recap and Q&A

Educator should recap in two minutes by highlighting:

- i. reasons why addiction is a medical problem and
- ii. drug abuse preventive strategies. Then, allow for questions.

References

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TAKE HOME LEAFLET

English Version

This leaflet contains a summary of the modules of structured health education program on use of psychoactive substances among inter-state commercial drivers in Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria.

A. What is drug abuse?

When a drug is used in pattern that is damaging the physical, mental, and or social wellbeing.

Examples of physical damages: damages to the lungs, liver, kidney, brain etc.

Examples of damages to mental health: addiction, depression and loss of touch from reality

Examples of social damages: financial losses, interpersonal relationship losses.

B. What is a drug of abuse?

A drug of abuse is any chemical or substance that when taken into the body, can alter brain function in terms of the way we think, we perceive things, we react emotionally to situations, and the way we behave.

C. Types of drugs of abuse

12. Tobacco (cigar, taaba e.t.c)
13. Alcohol (commercial e.g beer, wine, branded spirit)
14. Alcohol (non-commercial e.g emu, ogogoro e.t.c)
15. Cannabis/Indian hemp/marijuana (weed, Igbo, smoke, skunk, Arizona, Colorado, Loud, skushy etc.)
16. Mild stimulants (e.g. kolanut, orogbo, coffee).
17. Other major stimulants (e.g. Cocaine, Amphetamine, Pro-plus, Dexamphetamine, Ephedrine, Kwaya, Mkpururimi).

18. Sedatives (Sleeping tablets e.g., Valium, Librium, Mogadon) without prescription by doctors.
19. Opioids (Fentanyl, Heroin, Pentazocine, Tramadol, Cough syrup with codeine, Codeine tablets)
20. Sniffing agents (e.g. petrol, glue, solvents etc).
21. Anabolic steroids (Winstrol, Dianabol) without doctor's prescription.

D. Complications of using drugs among commercial drivers

- Use of drugs puts a driver at risk of Road traffic accident
- Use of drugs puts a driver at risk of cancer and other various damages to the organs of the body e.g. lungs, kidneys, liver, intestines, mouth, heart etc.
- Use of drugs can put a driver at risk of mental illness

E. Identifying drivers with drug use problems

- They may easily get angry and get into frequent fights with co-drivers, family and loved ones.
- They may start to avoid going out with colleagues to social events and may even frequently miss union meetings.
- They may be noticed to have difficulty taking care of their personal hygiene.
- They may have sleep and appetite problems
- While driving, one may notice reduced concentration, frequent yawning, hands and body shaking, sweatiness, increased heart beats, restless and generally increased level of discomfort.

F. What Are Your Roles as A Driver in The Prevention and Treatment of Drug Abuse?

1. Counselling and helping other people with drug use problems

2. Appropriate referral to hospital (DATER centre and other drug treatment centres across the country)

Thank you for taking out your time to attend the educational program!

Yoruba Version

Iwe pelebe yi ni isonisoki eto eko ilera fun ti lilo awon oogun afesodi laarin awon awako, ni ilu ilorin, ipinle kwara.

A. Kini ilokulo oogun?

Ti eyan ba lo oogun ni ona to se ijamba fun ara, okan ati/tabii awujo.

Apeere ijamba ti ara ni: bibaje ti edo fooro, edo, kindinrin, opolo, ati beebelo.

Apeere ijamba ti okan ni: afesodi, irewesi okan, idamu ati beebelo.

Apeere ijamba ti awujo ni: adanu owo, ikuna ibasepo.

B. Kini awon oogun isilo?

Eyi ni awon nkan elo tabii kemikali, ti won ma n fa iyipada si bi opolo se n sise ti eyan ba lo won.

C. Apeere awon oogun isilo

- Tobacco (siga, taba)
- Oti (emu, oti bia, waini, emu, ogogoro ati beebelo)
- Indian hemp (Igbo, ewe, eja)
- Kola, orogbo, coffee
- Cocaine
- Oogun orun (valium)
- Oogun iko, Tramal, Codeine

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- Petrol, Glue (Gum), Paint
- Oogun steroids (mawu mawu)

D. Ijamba oogun isilo

- Oogun isilo le fa ewu oko fun awako.
- Oogun isilo le fa cancer, tabi aisan awon eya ara bi kindirin fun awako.
- Oogun isilo le fa aisan opolo fun awako.

E. Ona igbese lati mo awako to n lo Oogun ni lokulo

- Awon awako to n si Oogun lo, maa n saba tete binu, won si maa n tete ja pelu molebi ati awon ore.
- Awon awako to n si Oogun lo, le ko lati lo ibi ise tabi ode.
- Awon awako to n si Oogun lo, le ma toju ara won bi ti tele.
- Awon awako to n si Oogun lo, le ni isoro pelu orun sisun ati ounje jije.
- Eeyan le se aki yesi pe awon awako to n si Oogun lo, le ma fi ojusi nkan bo se ye, won tun le ma yaan ju bo se ye lo, won le ma laagun pupo, ara won le ma gbon, ati beebelo.

F. Awon igbese ti awako le se lati faa idena, ati itoju fun Oogun isilo

- Imoran ati iranlowo fun awon awako to n si Oogun lo.
- Di daari awon awako to n si Oogun lo si Ile iwosan fun itoju.

Ese pupo fun asiko yin o!